

Informal Learning, Apprenticeships, and Intellectual Networking in New Spain: The Case of Domingo Chimalpahin (1579-after 1640)

Aprendizaje Informal, Aprendices y Redes Intelectuales en la Nueva España: el Caso de Domingo Chimalpahin (1579-after 1640)

Carlos Diego Arenas Pacheco*

ABSTRACT: Research on the history of education in the Spanish Empire has generally focused on formal schooling for Spaniards or, more recently, for the children of Indigenous nobilities. To expand the scope of future research, this article proposes focusing on some avenues of informal learning that Indigenous intellectuals pursued to complement their basic formation at colonial schools. Domingo Chimalpahin (1579-ca. 1600), the most productive Nahuatl-language writer and historian in colonial Mexico, is a clear and relevant study case. Since we lack much of Chimalpahin's biographical data, previous research on him has suggested that elucidating specific details about his education could contribute not only to a better interpretation of his historical writings, but also to a deeper understanding of routes of informal education for Indigenous intellectuals in colonial Mexico and Latin America. This article argues that informal learning provided Chimalpahin with the higher education he needed to craft his works.

KEYWORDS: informal education; networking; New Spain; colonial education; colonial Mexico; Chimalpahin

RESUMEN: La investigación sobre la educación en el Imperio español se ha centrado generalmente en la escolarización de los españoles y de los hijos de la nobleza indígena. Para ampliar el alcance de futuras investigaciones, este artículo propone centrarse en algunas vías de aprendizaje informal que intelectuales indígenas siguieron para complementar su formación básica en las escuelas coloniales. Domingo Chimalpahin (1579-ca. 1600), el escritor en lengua náhuatl más productivo del México colonial, es un caso de estudio relevante. Investigaciones previas sobre Chimalpahin han sugerido que encontrar detalles específicos sobre su educación podría contribuir no solo a una mejor interpretación de sus escritos, sino también a una comprensión más profunda de las rutas de educación informal para los intelectuales indígenas en el México colonial y América Latina. Este artículo sostiene que el aprendizaje informal proporcionó a Chimalpahin la educación superior que necesitaba para elaborar sus obras.

PALABRAS CLAVE: educación informal; *networking*; Nueva España; educación colonial; México colonial; Chimalpahin

[...] just like our lord God is only one but also triple [...] so is the soul also one, but threefold in power: the first one is memory [...] and the intellect [...] and the will.¹

This Nahuatl-language rendition of a fragment from Augustine's *On the Trinity* appears in the *Primera Relación* of Domingo Francisco de San Antón Muñón Chimalpahin Cuauhtlehuanitzin (1579-after 1640), a Nahuatl-speaking Indigenous intellectual² living and writing in Mexico City at the

* Mexicano. Doctor en Estudios Medievales, University of Notre Dame, Indiana, Estados Unidos. Profesor-Investigador en la Escuela de Pedagogía de la Universidad Panamericana, Ciudad de México. Correo: cdarenas@up.edu.mx ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2494-0999>

¹ «yn iuhqui yehuatzin totecuiyo Dios ca zan huel cetzin auh yn iyeitilliztzin... auh yn ánima zanno ce, auh yetlamantli ytech ca huellitilliztli: yn iccentlamantli yehuatl yn tlnamiquilliztli... auh yn tlamachilliztli... auh yn tlanequilliztli». Domingo Chimalpahin, *Las Ocho Relaciones y el Memorial de Colhuacan* (Ciudad de México: CONACULTA, 1998), 1:48.

² I adopt the term Indigenous intellectual following Gabriela Ramos and Yanna Yannakakis, *Indigenous Intellectuals: Knowledge, Power, and Colonial Culture in Mexico and the Andes* (Durham: Duke University

beginning of the seventeenth century—and the most important and productive Indigenous-language historian of early New Spain.³ His eight *Relaciones* are a collection of manuscripts that tell the history of the Nahua peoples of central Mexico from Creation to 1591 and insert it into the Christian conception of universal salvific history.⁴ The *Primera* and the *Segunda Relaciones* treat of Creation, human nature, the dating of Jesus Christ's birth, and synchronize the Indigenous and the European calendars. Both *Relaciones*, but particularly the *Primera*, contain numerous references and quotations from European authors: a quotation from Plato's *Timaeus* leads to translations from Sophocles and Augustine, as well as references to Diogenes Laertius, Lactantius, Eusebius, Antonius Sabellicus, Thomas Aquinas, John Damascene, and Pseudo-Dionysus the Areopagite, among others. Meanwhile, the *Segunda* contains a translation from a contemporaneous cosmographical treatise and almanac, Henrico Martínez' *Reportorio*.⁵ Chimalpahin was thus not only an erudite regarding ancient and medieval philosophy and theology—he also knew the scholarship of his time.

Scholars assessing Chimalpahin's erudition have offered some partial explanations for it: perhaps he knew Latin and was able to consult sources in that language;⁶ perhaps he acquired knowledge from a «presbítero cualquiera en una ermita» or a secondary education in «algún colegio franciscano o, mejor aún, al jesuita», located in Mexico City.⁷ However, scholars lack more specific details of Chimalpahin's education and the source of his erudition: given that Chimalpahin was not a *pilli*—plural *pipiltin*—or Indigenous nobleman, he had no access to the most important schools for the Indigenous noble youth in Mexico City, like the Imperial College of Santa Cruz de Tlatelolco, where students received a thorough Humanistic formation in Latin language and literature.⁸

In short, the question is: since he had little access to formal education, how did Chimalpahin, a *macehualli*—plural *macehualtin*—or commoner from Chalco Amaquemecan—an *altepetl* or city

Press, 2014) and the many scholars who have underscored the intellectual agency of Indigenous writers in the Spanish colonies. Chimalpahin was an Indigenous intellectual in the sense that, as a scholar knowledgeable in Nahua and European writing scripts and historical traditions, he produced a written work that sought to have both a literary and a political impact in his social context.

³ As Chimalpahin is cited practically by all historians of early colonial Mexico, it is impossible to provide here a comprehensive bibliography. In addition to the sources cited in this article, I highlight Susan Schroeder, *Chimalpahin and the Kingdoms of Chalco* (Tucson, University of Arizona Press, 1991), a foundational monograph for all Chimalpahin-related studies. The *Relaciones* are published with a Spanish translation in Chimalpahin 1998, in two volumes. There is no complete English translation.

⁴ Richard Herzog, «Conferring a Universal Scope to Nahua Political Concepts. An Aim in the Works of Domingo Chimalpahin (Early 17th Century)», in *Indigenous Knowledge as a Resource: Transmission, Reception, and Interaction of Knowledge between the Americas and Europe, 1492–1800*, ed. by Laura Dierksmeier, Fabian Fechner, and Kazuhisa Takeda (Tübingen: Tübingen University Press), 125–143.

⁵ Henrico Martínez, *Reportorio de los tiempos, y historia natural desta Nueva España* (Alicante: self-published, 1606).

⁶ Jacqueline de Durand-Forest, «Extractos de la Primera Relación de Chimalpahin Quauhtlehuanitzin», *Estudios de Cultura Náhuatl* 20 (1990): 65–76; Elke Ruhnau, «The First Relation of Chimalpahin's Diferentes Historias Originales. Its Sources and the Author's Intention», *Indiana* 19/20 (2003): 277–287; S. A. D. Messiaen, «Some Interesting Observations on Chimalpahin by Use of His Diferentes Historias Originales», *Estudios de Cultura Náhuatl* 34 (2003): 219–256; Andrew Laird, «Universal History and New Spain's Indian Past: Classical Knowledge in Nahua Chronicles», *Bulletin of Latin American Research* 37, S1 (2018): 86–103; Camilla Townsend, *Fifth Sun: A New History of the Aztecs* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2019).

⁷ Clementina Battcock, «Chimalpahin, su formación y sus noticias sobre la presencia de la Iglesia Católica en Chalco Amaquemecan, siglos XVI–XVII», *Revista de Historia de América* 157 (2019): 71–85.

⁸ Andrew Laird, *Aztec Latin. Renaissance Learning and Nahuatl Traditions in Early Colonial Mexico* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2024).

located some 50 kilometers southeast of Mexico City—, was able to acquire the vast education and formation in European and Indigenous literacy, literature, and history that allowed him to write his massively important historical work?

This article aims to fill this gap in the literature by proposing that at least three routes of informal education or learning,⁹ namely 1) intergenerational learning, 2) apprenticeships, and 3) socialization, enculturation, and intellectual networking, were Chimalpahin's main ways into the world of books and history-writing. That is, instead of offering the simplistic explanation that Chimalpahin was an autodidact—an autonomous learner who worked independently—or that he was formally trained at an unspecified school—of which there is no mention or insinuation in his writings—, this article proposes to interpret Chimalpahin as a self-regulated, problem-solving, and socially embedded learner¹⁰ who, through specific processes of work-related learning, socialization, and enculturation, acquired the education required to identify and solve one of the main problems posed by the political and book culture of the early New Spain: the proper appraisal of Indigenous peoples, their history, and their place in books and world history.

Domingo Francisco: Chimalpahin's texts, his learning, and his early (in)formal education

Chimalpahin's historical writings are some of the most important sources for the general history of early New Spain, and arguably the most important Nahuatl-language sources for the precolonial and colonial history of the Indigenous peoples of central Mexico. His central work is comprised of his eight *Relaciones*. The overarching goal of the *Relaciones* was to demonstrate that Indigenous history was part of Christian salvific history and that, therefore, Indigenous peoples had the same dignity as Europeans. To achieve his goal, the historian based his arguments upon quotations from «autoridades históricas legitimadas por la tradición cristiana occidental, tales como los Padres de la Iglesia Católica Romana, y los filósofos de la antigüedad clásica europea».¹¹ Thus, crucial for Chimalpahin's goal was the production of Indigenous-language book—or books—that could engage in dialogue with European texts.

⁹ Following P. H. Coombs and M. Ahmed, *Attacking Rural Poverty: How Non-Formal Education Can Help* (Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 1974), 3-8, which proposed the division of styles of learning that is now almost standard in education research, formal learning is a near-synonym to formal schooling, namely «the institutionalized, chronologically graded and hierarchically structured... system, spanning lower primary school and the upper reaches of the university». In contrast, non-formal learning is, like a language learning app or a job-related course, «any organized, systematic, educational activity carried on outside the framework of the formal system to provide selected types of learning to particular subgroups in the population, adults as well as children». Informal learning is «the lifelong process by which every person acquires and accumulates knowledge, skills, attitudes, and insights from daily experiences and exposure to the environment». Thus, informal learning is less systematized and is inserted within the daily life of communities. Informal learning includes job-related learning and semi-structured learning from parents, relatives, peers, and mentors.

¹⁰ A recent trend in educational research focuses on what motivates self-regulated learners, including autodidacts, highly motivated students, and resourceful workers. One standard explanation is that problem-solving is a powerful motivator for informal and work-related learners. See, for instance, Anne Frieda Doris Kittel y Tina Seufert, «It's All Metacognitive: The Relationship between Informal Learning and Self-Regulated Learning in the Workplace», *PLOS ONE* 18, n.º 5 (2023): e0286065, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0286065>. Socially embedded learning refers to the fact that most learners, especially informal learners, seldom acquire an education outside of an engagement with their social networks. See, for instance, Bo Chang, «Knowledge Construction as Socially Embedded Collective Learning», *Proceedings of the Adult Education Research Conference* (2010), <https://newprairiepress.org/aerc/2010/papers/13>.

¹¹ Battcock, «Chimalpahin...»

In addition to the *Primera* and *Segunda*, briefly described above, the *Tercera* to the *Octava Relaciones* contain a colossal amount of information regarding, among many other subjects, the semi-mythical migration of the Nahuatl peoples from northern Mexico to the lives, deeds, and lineages of hundreds of Indigenous rulers; the foundation of the most important *altepetl*, like Tenochtitlan, Colhuacan, and Chalco; the arrival of Hernán Cortés and other Spaniards to Mexico; the fall of Tenochtitlan and the incorporation of other *altepetl* into the colonial system; and the most salient events of early colonial history throughout central Mexico. Drawn from Indigenous manuscripts written in the Mesoamerican pictographic script—called *amoxtili* in Nahuatl—the *Segunda* to the *Séptima Relaciones* are annals, divided by years identified by both their Indigenous and their European names—for instance, 3 BC is 1 Rabbit, 1492 is 13 Flint, 1521 is 3 House, and so on—. The *Octava Relación*, written in continuous prose but also based on *amoxtili*, focuses on the noble lineages of the *altepetl* around the Chalco area, offers solutions to contemporary issues regarding the rulership of some *altepetl*, and defends the transmission of nobility through the maternal line. The *Octava* shows that, apart from his purely scholarly interests, Chimalpahin saw history-writing as a method of solving contemporary political issues and gaining respect from his Spanish and Indigenous contemporaries. Chimalpahin's parents, although descendants of *pipiltin*, were considered *macehualtin* due to the interdiction of the matrilineal descent of nobility. Thus, in his eyes, he was a *pilli*—and history could help him prove it.¹²

Other writings by Chimalpahin include another manuscript known as the *Diario*, a collection of manuscripts known as the *Codex Chimalpahin*, a Spanish-language transcription of Francisco López de Gómara's *La Conquista de México* (1552), and various other smaller writings.¹³ The *Diario* can be read as a continuation to the *Relaciones*, as it offers an annal of events taking place in Mexico City between 1577 and 1615, most of which Chimalpahin witnessed first-hand. He reports on, for instance, the 1610 and 1614 Japanese embassies visiting Mexico City, as well as some academic events connected to the Royal and Pontifical University of Mexico. Continuing to display his familiarity with contemporaneous books and learning, Chimalpahin reveals his acquaintance with Teresa of Ávila's *Las Moradas*, the establishment of seminaries and Latin colleges, and his knowledge about some of the most salient intellectuals of his time, including the Spaniards Bernardino de Sahagún, Alonso de Molina, Juan de Torquemada, and Juan Bautista, as well as the Indigenous Antonio Valeriano. The *Diario* also shows a highly socially embedded Chimalpahin who kept apprised of some of the most important political and intellectual events and formed part of social circles that gained him entry into some of them.

Chimalpahin's knowledge of Spanish books and connections with Spaniards and Nahuas suggests he probably had a good command of Spanish in addition to Nahuatl. Chimalpahin's mastery of Spanish is exhibited above all by his transcription of Gómara's *Conquista*. Instead of copying the book verbatim, Chimalpahin proceeded like an editor and fact-checker throughout the

¹² Susan Schroeder, *Chimalpahin and the Kingdoms of Chalco* (Tucson, University of Arizona Press, 1991), 12; Carlos Macías Prieto, *Early Seventeenth Century Nahuatl Poetics: Domingo Chimalpahin and the Cemanahuac Archive* (doctoral thesis, UC Berkeley, 2020), 8-9.

¹³ The *Diario* with an English translation can be found in Domingo Chimalpahin, *Annals of His Time* (Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2006). The *Codex Chimalpahin*, also with an English translation, is published in Domingo Chimalpahin, *Codex Chimalpahin: Society and Politics in Mexico Tenochtitlan, Tlatelolco, Texcoco, Culhuacan, and Other Nahuatl Altepetl in Central Mexico*. 2 vols. (Norman: University of Oklahoma Press, 1997). Chimalpahin's version of the *Conquista*, with English translation, can be read in Domingo Chimalpahin, *Chimalpahin's Conquest: A Nahuatl Historian's Rewriting of Francisco Lopez de Gomara's La conquista de México* (Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2010).

text.¹⁴ The author added, removed, and modified numerous details that he considered erroneous or incomplete in his source text by using other sources, including Spanish and Indigenous books, as well as oral testimonies. Thus, in addition to displaying Chimalpahin's confidence as a scholar through his development of a critical historiographical methodology, the *Conquista* can be read as a linguistic exercise of deletion, modification, and amplification that can only be performed by someone mastering a language—at least in its written form. Based on his networks and his rewriting of a Spanish book, we can safely assume that, at least in his later years, Chimalpahin's level of oral and written Spanish level was considerably high.

According to his *Relaciones*, Chimalpahin was born on May 26, 1579—year 9 Reed—, in the *altepetl* of Amaquemecan. As a *macehualli*, his baptismal name was simply Domingo Francisco. Dual first names were usual among Indigenous commoners, while most nobles generally bore bicultural names and last names—for instance, another Nahuatl historian and *pilli* was called Hernando de Alvarado Tezozómoc.¹⁵ The rest of his long bicultural name, namely «de San Antón Muñón Chimalpahin Quauhtlehuanitzin», were the last names that Chimalpahin gave himself in his writings as part of his authorial and social self-representation. Beyond evincing his desire to be recognized as a *pilli*, his self-imposed names reveal Chimalpahin's lifelong social, cultural, and educational engagements.

Chimalpahin was indeed descended from *pipiltin* from both his mother and his father's side. The loss of his immediate family's *pilli* status was quite recent: his maternal grandfather was don Domingo Hernández Ayopochtzin, while his paternal grandmother was doña Luisa Xochiquetzaltin. Their bicultural names, in addition to their bearing of the titles of don/doña, show that they were both considered *pipiltin*. It is possible that Chimalpahin's parents, María Jerónima Xiuhtotzin and Juan Agustín Ixpintzin, had a somewhat complicated status due to being illegitimate children or not completely favored by their relatives.¹⁶ In any case, despite his *macehualli* status, he seems to have had a good connection to *pipiltin*, including don Domingo, his maternal uncle don Diego Hernández, and other nobles from Amaquemecan and the Chalco area.¹⁷

Don Domingo, at least according to Chimalpahin's testimony, was fully literate in Nahuatl in alphabetical and Mesoamerican scripts. He wrote a book that contained information gathered from other written Indigenous sources, most notably from a book written by don Francisco Cuetzpaltzin, another of Chimalpahin's ancestors. Don Domingo's book was inherited by Agustín, Chimalpahin's father, who in turn passed it over to his son. Whether Agustín was literate or not, Chimalpahin's testimony suggests that scholarship and writing were important elements within his family, especially its *pipiltin* members.¹⁸

It is reasonable to affirm that the boy Chimalpahin became familiar with literacy and its importance in his early years. However, it is impossible to measure the extent to which his relatives taught him reading and writing, especially given his challenged social status. At the minimum, it is safe to assume that Chimalpahin, like many other Indigenous peoples in colonial Mexico, acquired at the very least what some scholars have called «mini-literacy»: namely, a form of partial literacy that serves «intra-ethnic, family purposes»,¹⁹ including maintaining and strengthening group identity,

¹⁴ Heather J. Allen, «Scribal Voices in Chimalpahin's Transcription of La Conquista de México», *Colonial Latin American Review* 31, n.º 1 (2022): 31–56

¹⁵ See James Lockhart, *The Nahuas after the Conquest* (Stanford: Stanford University Press, 1992), 117-130

¹⁶ Schroeder, *Chimalpahin...*, 10.

¹⁷ Chimalpahin, *Las ocho relaciones...*, 2:302-308, 2:346-348.

¹⁸ Chimalpahin, *Las ocho relaciones...*, 2:304.

¹⁹ F. Dubin, «Situating Literacy Within Traditions of Communicative Competence», *Applied Linguistics* 10, 2 (1989): 176-177.

participating at least minimally in Spanish colonial bureaucracy, and, perhaps more importantly, recognizing the symbolic and institutional value of the written word.

Like other Indigenous groups throughout the Americas,²⁰ Chimalpahin's *pipiltin* relatives and community contacts safeguarded books and old *amoxtli* or alphabetical manuscripts in their houses as symbolic and potentially juridical objects: it was record-keeping that preserved accounts of a family's lineage and could offer proofs of nobility, land ownership, or even the right to rule. Scholars investigating other aspects of literacy and record-keeping in the Black and Indigenous Americas have highlighted the importance of recognizing this form of mini-literacy as a valid and multi-faceted application of knowledge of letters—alphabetical and Indigenous—, one with deep social importance for individuals and communities alike.²¹ The same applies to knowledge of the colonial language: like other Indigenous peoples, we can assume that Chimalpahin and his family had, at the minimum, a passive knowledge of basic Spanish.²²

While Chimalpahin was a master at reading Mesoamerican script and using *amoxtli* as historical sources,²³ it is unclear whether he knew how to use the script actively. The manuscript of his *Diario*²⁴ contains the only two instances of Chimalpahin writing in the Mesoamerican script: for 1613, year 4 House, and 1614, year 5 Rabbit, the author included their respective glyphs in the traditional script.²⁵ The House sign is well-drawn, perhaps too well—in addition to its surrounding square cartouche, it is composed of only straight lines, and it seems Chimalpahin used a ruler to draw them. Traditional *tlahcuilohqueh*—scribes, sing. *tlahcuiloh*—drew the sign or the cartouches freehand, using more naturally drawn straight lines. Meanwhile, Chimalpahin drew the double square cartouche surrounding the Rabbit glyph more naturally, seemingly without a ruler. However, the Rabbit is drawn with a more Europeanized iconography than in traditional *amoxtli*, which generally have the Rabbit's head placed horizontally, with a round eye representing the *ixtli*—eye—glyph and its two frontal teeth showing. Once again, Chimalpahin's design of his two glyphs suggests that he was not fully trained as a traditional *tlahcuiloh*—while he had an active command of the writing system, he possessed little active knowledge of traditional iconography.

Figures 1 and 2. Details from Chimalpahin's *Diario*, Bibliothèque nationale de France, MS Mexicain 220, 198, 238 (source: gallica.bnf.fr/Bibliothèque nationale de France)

²⁰ See, for instance, Ethelia Ruiz Medrano, *Mexico's Indigenous Communities: Their Lands and Histories, 1500-2010* (Boulder: University Press of Colorado, 2010), 114-137.

²¹ See, for instance, José Ramón Jouve Martín, *Esclavos en la ciudad letrada: Esclavitud, escritura y colonialismo en Lima (1650-1700)* (Lima: Instituto de Estudios Peruanos, 2005).

²² Lockhart, *The Nahuas...*, 284-304.

²³ Alejandra Dávila Montoya, «Entre mexicas y chalcas: El tlatocayotl de Ecatepec a través de las Crónicas de Chimalpahin», *Revista de Historia de América* 165 (2023): 35-64.

²⁴ Bibliothèque nationale de France, MS Mexicain 220.

²⁵ See Figures 1 and 2.

After having had an informal, intergenerational exposition, even if partial, to alphabetical and Mesoamerican literacy within his family circle, the young Chimalpahin very likely began his first steps in formal education by attending the local school for Indigenous children managed by Dominican friars at their Our Lady of the Assumption convent in Amaquemecan.²⁶

Local schools like Chimalpahin's, generally known as *doctrinas* or *escuelas de doctrina*, were founded and managed mainly by Franciscans, Dominicans, and Augustinians throughout some of the most important *altepetl* throughout central Mexico.²⁷ In contrast to the most important schools, like Imperial College of Santa Cruz de Tlatelolco, local schools were not, in any way, grammar schools aiming at the full intellectual or professional education of their children—almost always boys.²⁸ Although the curriculum changed from school to school, most *doctrinas* functioned the same way: being primarily catechetical schools, teachers taught mostly *pipiltin* children basic alphabetical literacy in the local Indigenous language, sometimes including some basic Spanish and Latin, with the chief objective of having the children memorize the essential prayers—*Pater Noster*, *Ave Maria*, *Credo*, etc.—, internalize their new faith, and support the small number of Spanish friars in liturgical and record-keeping tasks. Beyond a basic formation in alphabetical literacy and liturgical music, some schools offered advanced education in plastic arts and writing, especially for those

²⁶ Battcock, «Chimalpahin...»

²⁷ Despite its age, Robert Ricard, *La conquista espiritual de México: Ensayo sobre el apostolado y los métodos misioneros de las órdenes mendicantes en la Nueva España de 1523-1524 a 1572* (México: Fondo de Cultura Económica, 2014 [1933]) still contains important information regarding schools for Indigenous children.

²⁸ Although there were some short-lived schools for Indigenous girls; see Josefina Muriel, «Los colegios de niñas indígenas en el siglo XVI», in *La sociedad novohispana y sus colegios de niñas. Tomo I: Fundaciones del siglo XVI* (México: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Instituto de Investigaciones Históricas, 2004), 59-104.

trained to become notaries and bureaucrats within local administrations. Advanced training, however, was mostly the privilege of a few local *pipiltin* teenagers. Some schools for *pipiltin* children were residential—most notably, Santa Cruz de Tlatelolco—, but whether Our Lady of the Assumption was one of them is unknown. Most *macehualtin* children, in contrast, only learned the basics of the faith and the prayers from oral preaching in the atria of churches.²⁹

While there is no concrete evidence that Chimalpahin attended Our Lady of the Assumption—he doesn't mention the school in his writings—, scholars assume it as a very likely possibility given the *pilli* status of most of his extended family.³⁰ If that was so, Chimalpahin attended the *escuela* for an unknown number of years between the ages of five or six and fifteen.³¹ There, he became a fully catechized and fully enculturated member of the still-young Mexican Catholic Church. Chimalpahin learned to read and very probably to write, adopted forms of behavior acceptable for colonial society, and, perhaps more importantly for his future education, became accustomed to navigating relationships between Indigenous societies and the Spanish.

Whether Chimalpahin attended Our Lady of the Assumption, intergenerational learning was essential for his early acquaintance with Mesoamerican and alphabetical literacy. While we can only gauge the degree of some elements of his informal education—i.e., his little active knowledge of the Mesoamerican script and his strong networking abilities with his extended family and the *pipiltin* in the Chalco area—, Chimalpahin the historian could not have existed without the learning he acquired from his immediate and extended family.

de San Antón: work-related learning and Chimalpahin's—possible—apprenticeship at San Antonio Abad

However basic or advanced Chimalpahin's early education was, his formation could not have been enough to make him a professional scribe, let alone the ambitious historian he eventually became. For that, and for the most concrete need of securing a livelihood based on what must have been the early signs of a talent for reading, writing, and record-keeping, Chimalpahin needed to move beyond the opportunities afforded at Amaquemecan.

At the age of fourteen, in 1593, Chimalpahin moved to Mexico City to begin working at the *ermita* or local shrine of San Antonio—or Antón—Abad, located in the *barrio* of Xolloco, some 1.4 kilometers south of the cathedral in the city center.

As their name suggests, Spanish *ermitas*—lit. hermitages—were originally sites associated with a hermit or small group of religious men who settled near an urban center to lead a life of relative seclusion that could serve as an example to the local population. In New Spain, while some *ermitas* were indeed inhabited by semi-hermits—for instance, fray Martín de Valencia's hermitage in Amaquemecan—, others were founded by conquistadores and other Spaniards as hermit-less shrines to thank specific saints for their success.

The San Antón *ermita* was founded in 1530 by a certain Alonso Sánchez—and continued to be under the patronage of who seem to be Alonso's descendants or younger relatives, most notably

²⁹ José María Kobayashi, *La educación como conquista: Empresa Franciscana en México* (Quito: Abya-Yala, 1996), 188; Battcock, «Chimalpahin...».

³⁰ José Rubén Romero Galván, «Chimalpahin Cuauhtlehuanitzin», in *Historiografía mexicana. Volumen I: Historiografía novohispana de tradición indígena*, edited by Juan A. Ortega y Medina, Rosa Camelo, and José Rubén Romero Galván (México: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Instituto de Investigaciones Históricas, 2003), 331; Battcock, «Chimalpahin...».

³¹ The student age interval reported by colonial school administrators. Before five or six years, children were deemed too young to learn; after puberty, they were deemed too unruly. See Ernesto de la Torre Villar, «Fray Pedro de Gante, maestro y civilizador de América», *Estudios de Historia Novohispana* 5, n.º 5 (1974): <https://doi.org/10.22201/iih.24486922e.1974.005.3252>; Kobayashi, *La educación...*, 56.

don Sancho Sánchez de Muñón, *maestrescuela* or scholaster of the Pontifical University of Mexico, and a certain don Diego de Muñón.³² In 1562, Sancho Sánchez and Claudio Arciniega, master builder at the Cathedral, renovated and enlarged the *ermita*, which led to the formation of a confraternity of Spaniards patronizing the shrine. The local Indigenous population also visited the shrine and was associated with the confraternity as producers of religious artwork. Originally managed by the local Franciscan mission—the *doctrina* of San Pablo—the *ermita* fell under the authority of the secular priesthood attached to the Cathedral.³³

We will turn to the Muñón family in the following section. For now, let us note that Chimalpahin clearly took pride in his work at San Antón—so much so that one of his self-fashioned last names connected him to the *ermita*. After all, it was at San Antón that Domingo Francisco became Chimalpahin the historian. That sole reason should suffice for historians of Chimalpahin and Indigenous education in colonial Mexico to consider the San Antón *ermita* as his main learning space.³⁴ In other words, I argue that, instead of speculating whether Chimalpahin attended any nearby school, we should see his work experience at San Antón as the secondary education that complemented his intergenerational—and probably his formal—learning at Amaquemecan.

Being only a teenager, Chimalpahin was sent to Mexico City, probably by *pipiltin* relatives who had connections in the Xollocó *barrio*. Be as it may, Chimalpahin eventually became the shrine's *mayoral*—that is, a kind of prefect or sacristan. In his adult years, Chimalpahin became, in other words, the highest Indigenous authority at San Antón.³⁵ His host of professional tasks included managing Indigenous parishioners, acting as a Spanish-Nahuatl interpreter, keeping the shrine in working order—and, most importantly, maintaining the *ermita*'s archive as its scribe, recording everything from baptisms to the shrine's finances. His job afforded him access to the large quantities of expensive paper and ink that he used for his writing and the shrine's records, as well as to the training required to manage an archive, historical or otherwise.

If San Antón was so important for a cadre of powerful Spaniards and Indigenous neighbors when Chimalpahin arrived, then we can affirm that the *ermita*'s significance was not new. The *ermita* needed an Indigenous *mayoral* before Chimalpahin's time. Although we have no information about the *mayoral* or *mayorales* preceding Chimalpahin, it is clear that someone must have formed the young writer as the shrine's record-keeper, whether a previous *mayoral* or the *ermita*'s priest. One of the usual roads into specialist professions in the Spanish world was training through apprenticeships:³⁶ a child, most often a boy, was sent by their parents to live and work with a professional, who often but not always received a tuition payment. When the professional received no payment, it was because the child paid for their education through their work. This road into specialist professions, such as notarial practice and other forms of archive-keeping, has been well-studied for the Andean case,³⁷ but its functioning in Mexico was very similar. In Mexico City, for

³² Romero Galván, «Chimalpahin...», 332–333; Battcock, «Chimalpahin...»

³³ Battcock, «Chimalpahin...»; Rodrigo Martínez Baracs, «El Diario de Chimalpáhin», *Estudios de Cultura Náhuatl* 38 (diciembre de 2007), <https://nahuatl.historicas.unam.mx/index.php/ecn/article/view/9355>.

³⁴ A learning space or environment is the physical environment where a learner acquires or develops new knowledge. Workspaces act as learning spaces for the acquisition of work-related knowledge. See Maggi Savin-Baden, *Learning Spaces: Creating Opportunities for Knowledge Creation in Academic Life* (New York: McGraw Hill, 2008), 5–34.

³⁵ Martínez Baracs, «El Diario...», 289.

³⁶ See, for instance, Nayeli Majía, «Aprendices, oficiales y maestros según los Protocolos de la Notaría No. 1 de Toluca. 1560–1725» (Licenciatura thesis, Universidad Autónoma del Estado de México, 2022); Zandra Pérez Velasco, «Los escribientes españoles e indígenas y el proceso de alfabetización en España y en México durante el s. XVI», *Revista de Lenguas y Literatura Indoamericanas* 22, n.º 1 (2021): 65–125.

³⁷ Kathryn Burns, *Into the Archive: Writing and Power in Colonial Peru* (Durham: Duke University Press, 2010).

instance, there were Indigenous professional guilds—*gremios*—of plastic artists and other specialists who trained the new generations, in addition to helping artists find work and protect their interests.³⁸

Given how specialists were typically trained and found jobs in the Spanish world, Chimalpahin became a *mayoral* and a professional scribe not because of having attended a school, but because he was an apprentice learning a record-keeping profession. The future historian found an opportunity at San Antón, perhaps because of family connections or simply luck. It was at the *ermita* that, as an apprentice to the previous *mayoral* or the shrine's priest, Chimalpahin continued his formation as a professional scribe and received the advanced training he needed to work with paper and ink, manage an archive, read and write books, and continue building strong social networks. It was at San Antón, for instance, where he developed his characteristic hand, a highly legible *bastarda* with a high level of cursivity, wide letters, few corrections, and very few ligatures or abbreviations. Such an advanced, smooth-flowing, clear, and legible hand could not have been developed by someone who didn't have numerous opportunities to practice his writing, whether as an apprentice to a scribe or as a professional working with texts every day.³⁹

Through his job at San Antón, Chimalpahin completed his education in literacy. It was also where he acquired mastery over the Spanish language, a closer acquaintance with Latin, and a deeper relationship with European books. His everyday work, whether as an apprentice or as the *mayoral*, implied a constant relationship with the resident or visiting priests, lay Spaniards who visited the *ermita*, any Spanish tradesmen who offered services to the shrine, and San Antón's influential patrons. Therefore, his everyday work required both passive and active use of Spanish, allowing him to attend to the managerial tasks and solve the daily work-related problems. As the archive keeper of the shrine, he also needed to handle Spanish-language documentation, at least basic contracts and baptismal records. As the sacristan or main aid to the shrine's priest(s), Chimalpahin handled the liturgical, homiletic, and doctrinal books they required to perform their job—some of them probably in Latin.

Again, regardless of the level of literacy, Spanish, and Latin that Chimalpahin acquired at Amaquemecan, work-related learning completed his formation in European languages and books. We don't need to posit Chimalpahin's attendance at an undetermined school when the author himself tells us that his work at San Antón was integral to his identity as an author and historian.

Muñón Chimalpahin Cuauhtlehuantzin: socialization, enculturation, and intellectual networking in Chalco and Mexico City

Chimalpahin's identity and everyday experiences, like those of other Indigenous intellectuals throughout the colonial Americas, were complex: born as a *macehualli* boy within a *pilli* family with a strong intergenerational tradition of community record-keeping, his work-related learning brought him in direct contact with Spaniards, their language—or languages, if we include Latin—and their books. However, Chimalpahin's relationship with all these elements was not passive. Throughout his life, he maintained an active role in maintaining a dynamic network of Indigenous and Spanish contacts who supported his work as an archive keeper, whether as a *mayoral* or a historian. That is, to support his professional and intellectual pursuits, Chimalpahin made active use of the processes of socialization and enculturation to which young Indigenous students and workers were subjected under Spanish colonialism. His adoption of the last names «Muñón Chimalpahin Cuauhtlehuantzin»

³⁸ See, for instance, José Guadalupe Victoria, *Pintura y sociedad en Nueva España: siglo XVI* (México: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 1986).

³⁹ See Figures 1 and 2.

signals the historian's active navigation within the complex sociocultural and intellectual context of colonial New Spain.

Despite his problematic *macehualli* status within his *altepetl* and his early resettlement to Mexico City, Chimalpahin never lost contact with his relatives and the network of Indigenous historians who preceded him. As a true scholar, Chimalpahin went beyond the information presented by the book he inherited from his father Agustín and his maternal grandfather don Domingo, and gathered as many alphabetical, Mesoamerican-script, and oral sources as possible to compare, transcribe, translate, and collect into his work. As it has been argued in the case of Fernando de Alva Ixtlilxochitl,⁴⁰ Chimalpahin worked within a «native archive», namely an informal network of Indigenous, mestizo, and Spanish intellectuals sharing documents and discoveries among them. Chimalpahin's main «native archive» or network was the already existing network of historians in the Chalco region—and the historian made sure to utilize it as much as possible.

In a rare acknowledgment of his sources—a practice unusual even among European historians of his time—, Chimalpahin preserved in his *Octava Relación* the names of his main informants for that specific text. In addition to the book written by don Domingo, who «learned how to read books and how to write the alphabet», the historian also tells us that he used a book preserved by don Francisco Cuetzpaltzin, which was already used as a source by don Domingo; another book preserved by don Vicente de la Anunciación, Ayopochtzin's cousin; the oral testimony of don Baltasar Ahuilizatzin, Cuetzpaltzin's brother; yet another book preserved by don Bartolomé de Santiago Tenmahuitzin; and a book of annals written by don Feliciano de la Asunción Calmazacatzin.⁴¹ Chimalpahin's account, too long to include here, portrays a very strong native archive or intellectual network that was tremendously active and dynamic, at least in the generation before his. To legitimize his historical accounts, Chimalpahin depicts himself as the heir to such an Indigenous republic of letters, one in which writers and oral informants constantly collaborated to keep their community and family histories alive.

Chimalpahin used such information to report in his *Octava* the past and current issues regarding a succession polemic surrounding the current *tlahtoani* of Amaquemecan.⁴² Using Indigenous and Spanish sources, Chimalpahin argues against the Chalcans' interdiction of matrilineal succession to defend the case of another pretender to rulership—and, *en passant*, to support his status as a *pilli*. If Chimalpahin was granted access to so many documents to consult and people to interview, it means that, like Alva Ixtlilxochitl, the historian actively kept in touch with his connections in the Chalco area. It also means that, despite his *macehualli* status, he was known among members of the *pilli* class. Based on Chimalpahin's testimonies in the *Octava* regarding his interviews and his gathering of books, one can imagine Chimalpahin frequently traveling to Amaquemecan and the Chalco region to maintain contact with his parents—remember that his father bequeathed him don Domingo's book—, his extended family, and the Chalco native archive.

Chimalpahin's active process of socialization with his family and community gave Chimalpahin access to his diverse sources of Indigenous learning, support with reading and interpreting *amoxtli*, and information regarding the latest political disputes in Chalco. The historian left evidence of his active socialization in his name. To represent himself as a noble and bolster his family credentials, the historian adopted the names «Chimalpahin» and «Cuauhtlehuanitzin» from two ancient noble forefathers: from his father's side, he descended from the family of the Chalca *pilli* Chimalpahin—whom Domingo identifies with the epithet of *huehue*, the Elder, to distinguish his ancestor from

⁴⁰ Amber Brian, *Alva Ixtlilxochitl's Native Archive and the Circulation of Knowledge in Colonial Mexico* (Nashville: Vanderbilt University Press, 2016).

⁴¹ Chimalpahin, *Las ocho relaciones...*, 2:302-206, 346-348.

⁴² For Chimalpahin's use of other Mesoamerican sources, see Dávila Montoya, «Entre mexicas y chalcas...»

himself, the *yanquic* or Younger Chimalpahin—; from his mother’s side, the Younger Chimalpahin was a descendant of a Chalca *tlahtoani* or ruler, Cuauhtlehuanitzin. To further mark himself as a *pilli*, Chimalpahin included in his name the title of «don», following the model of names borne by the Spanish and Indigenous nobility.

Chimalpahin was also a masterful networker with Spaniards. As discussed in the previous section, Chimalpahin’s job opened the door for him to the Spanish colonial world. His connection to the main patron of the San Antón shrine, the *maestrescuela* Sancho Sánchez de Muñón, was especially significant for the historian—so much so that he adopted his last name. Many Indigenous peoples, both *pipiltin* and *macehualtin*, adopted the first or last names of Spaniards who played important roles in their lives, whether as godfathers, patrons, *encomenderos*, or otherwise.⁴³ Chimalpahin probably adopted Sancho’s last name because the *maestrescuela* was the main supporter of the San Antón *ermita*. But the historian’s relationship to Sancho probably went deeper than that. As it appears in Chimalpahin’s *Diario*, the historian was—or at least pretended to be—close to Sancho and his family, to the point of accompanying him to some events around Mexico City⁴⁴ and referring to him with lofty epithets such as «doctor»,⁴⁵ «great priest and savant»,⁴⁶ and «great priest and knower of Latin».⁴⁷ Chimalpahin also reports on the death of Leonor Marín, wife of Diego de Muñón, who were «patrons of the churchly home of lord San Antón Abad» and parents of fray Agustín del Espíritu Santo, an Antonine friar who acted as the *ermita*’s main chaplain and patron after Sancho’s death in December of 1600.⁴⁸ As suggested by previous scholars, it was fray Agustín who probably sanctioned Chimalpahin’s activities as a historian and supplied him with extra ink and paper, in addition to the required materials for the upkeep of the *ermita*.⁴⁹

In numerous other parts of the *Diario*, Chimalpahin tells us about his other Spanish acquaintances and his presence in other important events. For instance, he calls two Spaniards, the woodcarver Diego López and the lay Franciscan Elías, his «dear friends».⁵⁰ He was well-informed regarding how the Augustinian Gonzalo de Hermsillo obtained the Latin chair at the University, despite his opponent, Diego de Contreras, giving a good lecture «in Latin lore».⁵¹ He was able to gather information, some of which first-hand, regarding the Japanese embassies of 1610 and 1614 and how they interacted with the viceroy and other government and church notables in New Spain.⁵²

In short, while being attached to and proud of his identity as a Nahuatl from Amaquemecan, Chimalpahin was successful in becoming enculturated into colonial Spanish ways of life and its forms of socializing. Little of the information Chimalpahin registers in his *Diario* and his *Relaciones*, including his knowledge of «autoridades históricas legitimadas por la tradición cristiana occidental», could have been obtained if he remained secluded in his *ermita* without becoming an active member of colonial society. As scholars discussing Alva Ixtlilxochitl have argued,⁵³ most lettered members of both Spanish and Indigenous societies shared their knowledge within their network, whether by lending books and manuscripts or by pointing their connections to sources of information. Thus,

⁴³ Lockhart, *The Nahuas...*, 117-130.

⁴⁴ Chimalpahin, *Annals...*, 52-53.

⁴⁵ Chimalpahin, *Annals...*, 30-31.

⁴⁶ Chimalpahin, *Annals...*, 52-53.

⁴⁷ Chimalpahin, *Annals...*, 70-71.

⁴⁸ Chimalpahin, *Annals...*, 70-71, 172-173.

⁴⁹ Susan Schroeder, *Tlaxcala Remembered: Mastermind of the Aztec Empire* (Norman: University of Oklahoma Press, 2016), 112.

⁵⁰ Chimalpahin, *Annals...*, 160-161, 216-217.

⁵¹ Chimalpahin, *Annals...*, 270-271.

⁵² Chimalpahin, *Annals...*, 170-173, 272-277.

⁵³ Brian, *Alva Ixtlilxochitl’s Native Archive...*

while it is not wrong to affirm that Chimalpahin obtained his erudition or his books from a «presbítero cualquiera en una ermita»,⁵⁴ I argue that it is crucial to see Chimalpahin as an active seeker of such knowledge. His intellectual active and dynamic intellectual networks—and friendships—are the key to understand Chimalpahin’s education—it is not necessary to speculate about unidentified schools.

Conclusion: reappraising the education of Indigenous intellectuals in early colonial Mexico

As demonstrated by many Indigenous intellectuals today,⁵⁵ it is not necessary to attend formal schooling to attain knowledge—informal education, whether acquired through intergenerational learning, work-related experience, socialization, and networking, can provide learners a solid higher education otherwise unavailable.

Using contemporary distinctions between learning styles, this article has shown that the education of Indigenous intellectuals in colonial Mexico, particularly that of Chimalpahin, should not require researchers to focus solely on formal education. While research on known schools—San José de los Naturales, Santa Cruz de Tlatelolco, etc.—is certainly essential, applying modern understandings of education and the ways to obtain and develop learning can help us on at least three fronts: 1) properly assessing Indigenous forms of education—intergenerational learning, for instance—outside of formal schooling, 2) considering Indigenous intellectuals as active constructors of their learning, and 3) going beyond the Indigenous intellectual as an isolated individual and begin interpreting their works as the fruit of knowledge-sharing within intellectual networks. While Indigenous writers like Chimalpahin might appear isolated given the current availability of sources and our tendency to consider authors as sole creators of their works, historians of education need to move beyond the current centrality of school education better to approach the real educational experiences of Indigenous intellectuals.

Bibliography

- Allen, Heather J. «Scribal Voices in Chimalpahin’s Transcription of *La Conquista de México*». *Colonial Latin American Review* 31, n.º 1 (2022): 31–56.
- Battcock, Clementina. «Chimalpahin, su formación y sus noticias sobre la presencia de la Iglesia Católica en Chalco Amaquemecan, siglos XVI–XVII». *Revista de Historia de América* 157 (2019): 71–85.
- Bibliothèque nationale de France, MS Mexicain 220.
- Brian, Amber. *Alva Ixtlilxochitl’s Native Archive and the Circulation of Knowledge in Colonial Mexico*. Nashville.: Vanderbilt University Press, 2016.
- Burns, Kathryn. *Into the Archive: Writing and Power in Colonial Peru*. Durham: Duke University Press, 2010. JSTOR. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv11smfxs>.
- Chang, Bo. «Knowledge Construction as Socially Embedded Collective Learning». *Proceedings of the Adult Education Research Conference* (2010). <https://newprairiepress.org/aerc/2010/papers/13>.
- Chimalpahin, Domingo. *Annals of His Time*. Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2006.

⁵⁴ Battcock, «Chimalpahin...»

⁵⁵ See, for instance, Kelly S. McDonough, *The Learned Ones: Nahua Intellectuals in Postconquest Mexico* (Tucson, University of Arizona Press, 2014).

- . *Codex Chimalpahin: Society and Politics in Mexico Tenochtitlan, Tlatelolco, Texcoco, Culhuacan, and Other Nahua Altepetl in Central Mexico*. 2 vols. Norman: University of Oklahoma Press, 1997.
- . *Chimalpahin's Conquest: A Nahua Historian's Rewriting of Francisco Lopez de Gomara's La conquista de México*. Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2010.
- . *Las ocho relaciones y el memorial de Colhuacan*. 2 vols. Mexico City: CONACULTA, 1998.
- Coombs, P. H., and M. Ahmed. *Attacking Rural Poverty: How Non-Formal Education Can Help*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 1974.
- Dávila Montoya, Alejandra. «Entre mexicas y chalcas: El tlatocayotl de Ecatepec a través de las *Crónicas de Chimalpahin*». *Revista de Historia de América* 165 (2023): 35-64.
- Dubin, F. «Situating Literacy Within Traditions of Communicative Competence». *Applied Linguistics* 10, n.º 2 (1989): 171-181.
- Durand-Forest, Jacqueline de. «Extractos de la Primera Relación de Chimalpahin Quauhtlehuanitzin». *Estudios de Cultura Náhuatl* 20 (1990): 65-76.
- Herzog, Richard. «Conferring a Universal Scope to Nahua Political Concepts. An Aim in the Works of Domingo Chimalpahin (Early 17th Century)». In *Indigenous Knowledge as a Resource: Transmission, Reception, and Interaction of Knowledge between the Americas and Europe, 1492-1800*, edited by Laura Dierksmeier, Fabian Fechner, and Kazuhisa Takeda, 125-143. Tübingen: Tübingen University Press.
- Jouve Martín, José Ramón. *Esclavos en la ciudad letrada: Esclavitud, escritura y colonialismo en Lima (1650-1700)*. Lima: Instituto de Estudios Peruanos, 2005.
- Kittel, Anne Frieda Doris, and Tina Seufert. «It's All Metacognitive: The Relationship between Informal Learning and Self-Regulated Learning in the Workplace». *PLOS ONE* 18, n.º 5 (2023): e0286065. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0286065>.
- Kobayashi, José María. *La educación como conquista: Empresa Franciscana en México*. Quito: Abya-Yala, 1996.
- Laird, Andrew. *Aztec Latin. Renaissance Learning and Nahuatl Traditions in Early Colonial Mexico*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2024.
- . «Universal History and New Spain's Indian Past: Classical Knowledge in Nahua Chronicles». *Bulletin of Latin American Research* 37, S1 (2018): 86-103.
- Lockhart, James. *The Nahuas after the Conquest*. Stanford: Stanford University Press, 1992.
- Macías Prieto, Carlos. *Early Seventeenth Century Nahua Poetics: Domingo Chimalpahin and the Cemanahuac Archive*. Doctoral thesis, UC Berkeley, 2020. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/8vb236h1>.
- Majía, Nayeli. «Aprendices, oficiales y maestros según los Protocolos de la Notaría No. 1 de Toluca. 1560-1725». Licenciatura thesis, Universidad Autónoma del Estado de México, 2022.
- Martínez, Henrico. *Reportorio de los tiempos, y historia natural desta Nueva España*. Alicante: self-published, 1606.
- Martínez Baracs, Rodrigo. «El Diario de Chimalpáhin». *Estudios de Cultura Náhuatl* 38 (diciembre de 2007). <https://nahuatl.historicas.unam.mx/index.php/ecn/article/view/9355>.
- McDonough, Kelly S. *The Learned Ones: Nahua Intellectuals in Postconquest Mexico*. Tucson: University of Arizona Press, 2014.
- Messiaen, S. A. D. «Some Interesting Observations on Chimalpahin by Use of His *Diferentes Historias Originales*». *Estudios de Cultura Náhuatl* 34 (2003): 219-256.
- Muriel, Josefina. «Los colegios de niñas indígenas en el siglo XVI». In *La sociedad novohispana y sus colegios de niñas. Tomo I: Fundaciones del siglo XVI*, 59-104. México: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Instituto de Investigaciones Históricas, 2004.

- Pérez Velasco, Zandra. «Los escribientes españoles e indígenas y el proceso de alfabetización en España y en México durante el s. XVI». *Revista de Lenguas y Literatura Indoamericanas* 22, n.º 1 (2021): 65–125.
- Ramos, Gabriela, and Yannis Yannakakis. *Indigenous Intellectuals: Knowledge, Power, and Colonial Culture in Mexico and the Andes*. Durham: Duke University Press, 2014.
- Ricard, Robert. *La conquista espiritual de México: Ensayo sobre el apostolado y los métodos misioneros de las órdenes mendicantes en la Nueva España de 1523-1524 a 1572*. México: Fondo de Cultura Económica, 2014.
- Romero Galván, José Rubén. «Chimalpain Cuauhtlehuanitzin». In *Historiografía mexicana. Volumen I: Historiografía novohispana de tradición indígena*, edited by Juan A. Ortega y Medina, Rosa Camelo, and José Rubén Romero Galván, 331-350. México: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Instituto de Investigaciones Históricas, 2003.
- Ruhnau, Elke. «The First Relation of Chimalpahin's *Diferentes Historias Originales*: Its Sources and the Author's Intention». *Indiana* 19/20 (2003): 277-287.
- Ruíz Medrano, Ethelia. *Mexico's Indigenous Communities: Their Lands and Histories, 1500-2010*. Boulder: University Press of Colorado, 2010.
- Savin-Baden, Maggi. *Learning Spaces: Creating Opportunities for Knowledge Creation in Academic Life*. New York: McGraw Hill, 2008.
- Schroeder, Susan. *Chimalpahin and the Kingdoms of Chalco*. Tucson: University of Arizona Press, 1991.
- . *Tlacaelel Remembered: Mastermind of the Aztec Empire*. Norman: University of Oklahoma Press, 2016.
- Torre Villar, Ernesto de la. «Fray Pedro de Gante, maestro y civilizador de América». *Estudios de Historia Novohispana* 5, n.º 5 (1974). <https://doi.org/10.22201/iih.24486922e.1974.005.3252>.
- Townsend, Camilla. *Fifth Sun: A New History of the Aztecs*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2019.
- Victoria, José Guadalupe. *Pintura y sociedad en Nueva España: siglo XVI*. México: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 1986.